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Sahel Collaboration and Communication Project (SCC)

RESILIENCE LEARNING BRIEF

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COLLABORATIVE MAPPING CLUB

A foundational element of the Sahel Collaboration and Communication (SCC) project design is to leverage spatial analytical techniques, Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and collaborative/participatory mapping to promote collaboration, learning and adaptation and resilience. Significant advancement of these activities was made with the high level of interest and partner participation in the Collaborative Mapping Club, the *Club de Cartographie Collaborative* (CCC).

The CCC is an informal weekly workshop led by SCC that presents interactive sessions to build capacity around the essential skills for collaborative and participatory mapping in support of resilience learning, adaptive management, and the sequencing, layering, and integrating through joint CLA efforts (Collaborating, Learning, and Adapting). This brief compares data from a baseline survey of CCC applicants prior to the sessions to a rapid survey of a sample of participants after completing a series of four CCC sessions. Participants' profiles and needs are presented followed by summarized statements of changes in GIS skills and spatial data management participants attribute to CCC engagement.

SAHEL COLLABORATION AND COMMUNICATION (SCC) IS IMPLEMENTED BY

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Four initial CCC sessions were designed through a consultation of Tulane University experts and Mercy Corps GIS staff from May to June 2022 that covered the themes of:

- Capturing geolocation data & rapid mapping with Google MyMaps
- Mapping points
- Map Symbology
- Advanced Symbology and introduction to categorized point mapping

Niger and Burkina CCCs met on alternative weeks. Approximately 30 participants registered in Niger and more than 20 attended each session. Burkina Faso had fewer registrations. Of these, average attendance in each of the four sessions ranged from 10-20. The participants gained basic familiarity with the Open Source QGIS and had practical experience with web-based tools like Google Maps and Google myMaps (see session facilitation plans and ppt-slides [here](#)). Sessions included presentations of key mapping topics and practical exercises provided as assignments for participants to apply those skills on their projects.

WHAT WE KNOW ABOUT CCC PARTICIPANTS

SESSION AND PARTICIPANT PROFILES

Fifty-nine (59) participants signed up for the CCC. There were more than 30 registered in Niger and more than 20 in Burkina Faso. There was a diverse and engaged group of CCC participants. Monitoring, Evaluation and Learning (MEL) officers were the largest group of participants (20). Technical experts or advisors from Health, Environment and Democracy were also significant (15). Other participants included Chiefs of Party (COP), Country Directors, and Deputy Chiefs of Party (DCOPs) alongside IT and administrative staff.

USE OF GIS BY PARTICIPANTS BEFORE CCC SESSIONS

About 35,1% of the CCC participants had used GIS before and 68,4% did not have any personal experience with GIS or mapping. Several people responded with ‘indicating interest but perhaps demand for additional capacity development to achieve mastery of GIS’. A few participants had used thematic maps and others had worked with land use maps. The most common use was for mapping project interventions.

Do you make maps or spatial analyses?

GIS ASPECTS THAT PARTICIPANTS WANT TO LEARN MORE ABOUT

The data and the sources of the data that participants wanted to learn to map were diverse. A large number (34,3%) were looking to map data they had collected on mobile phones. Another significant group (22,9%) had tables of statistical data for thematic mapping. Some data was in pdf of paper forms. One participant specifically wanted to use data collaboratively to create maps with partners.

What are you doing in terms of using map data in your project

REPORTED CHANGES IN PARTICIPANTS' GIS COMPETENCIES

To verify the effects that the first CCC sessions had on the interests and commitment of the partners and what could be improved in the follow-up sessions, during the month of September 2022, SCC staff conducted a rapid survey using an open-ended questionnaire focusing on significant changes. SCC selected respondents based on their attendance at sessions, but some were selected because they missed sessions. The rapid survey was built upon the pre-session capacity assessment using the same terminology and scope, but asking a set of questions adapted for open-ended interviews. This questionnaire was completed through online interviews with a sample of 10 people. This represents approximately 17% of those who completed the participation form and 25% of those who participated in the sessions. The following are some of the effects of the CCC sessions reported by the participants.

KEY FINDINGS OF EARLY SIGNIFICANT CHANGES

This survey confirmed that the CCC sessions led to significant changes in participants': i) use of mapping in their interventions and II) capacity to map their data.

USE OF MAPPING IN PARTNER INTERVENTIONS

Nine of ten of the participants surveyed said that the CCC sessions had contributed to increased use of mapping in their project interventions. In addition to the enthusiasm and curiosity that the sessions created about the use of GIS, they improved participants' abilities in several ways, including:

- Acquiring the ability to read maps more easily,
- Ability to indicate the focus of food insecurity on maps,
- Follow-up with field enumerators by verifying coordinates to ensure that they have collected data, and
- Including maps in their communications.

USE OF WHAT IS DISCUSSED AT THE CCC IN PARTICIPANTS' WORK

Five of ten - 50% of the people interviewed in the rapid follow-up survey say they have already used at least one of the points discussed during the sessions in their project activities. Those who said they had used the knowledge gained from the CCC in their work said they had used it to:

- Retrieve GPS coordinates to complete a database,
- Produce a mapping plan for the next quarter and then start producing maps,
- Map water points, and
- Develop a project to produce a map of the intervention area.

ADDITIONAL CAPACITY DEVELOPMENT NEEDED FOR PARTICIPANTS TO INDEPENDENTLY MAP DATA

According to the baseline survey, 35.1% of CCC participants had produced maps, compared to 68.1% who did not. After completing the four sessions, 40% said they were able to produce maps. This represents an increase of more than 4 points in the number of people who can map their data.

IMPLICATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FUTURE OF CCC

Ten of ten (100%) of those surveyed said that they strongly appreciated the CCC. The majority of those who attended did so to gain skills in map-making and geospatial analysis. For the CCC to achieve its objectives, they made recommendations focused on two aspects: session organization and technical priorities.

ON THE ORGANIZATION OF THE SESSIONS:

- Organize face-to-face sessions to allow for more interaction and practice
- Review the assignments, provide feedback and check if the participants have grey areas after the assignments, providing more practice of the content of the sessions
- Since the participants do not have the same level in GIS, it is necessary to organize the sessions according to the level of the participants by separating those who have knowledge in GIS from beginners
- Give more practical exercises
- Improve communication between participants and facilitators

THE ASPECTS ON WHICH FUTURE CCC SESSIONS SHOULD FOCUS INCLUDE:

- Data collection and mapping
- Mastering the use of software like QGIS or Kobocollect
- Production of legends
- Online interactive mapping
- Symbolologies (choice of symbols, placing them on maps, etc)

PRODUCTION TEAM

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